

Treatment of waste water from coke oven plant – A case study[†]

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Abstract : Industrial progress has been accompanied by a growing negative impact on the environment in terms of its pollution and degradation. In our country number of coke oven batteries for production of low ash metallurgical coke is increasing day by day. During off gas cleaning there are different sources of generation of waste water. But the waste water is not treated before discharge. Naturally found coal is converted into coke in coke ovens and a large quantity of water is used for quenching hot coke and for washing gas. Effluent generated contains high value of TSS, BOD, COD, phenols, ammonia, cyanide, which cause serious water pollution problems. This study was carried out to focus on characteristics of the effluent produced by coke oven plant and a treatability study was conducted to find out an appropriate treatment procedure to achieve a depletion of pollutants for discharge to surface water bodies after meeting the level of standard. This study was done initially separating ammonia of raw effluent through natural zeolite for ammonia scrubbing water. After this treatment the treated water was mixed with coal tar separator effluent, quenching effluent and gas plant effluent for chemical treatment followed by two stages aerobic biodegradation process and finally adsorption process by activated carbon. Overall depletion rate of COD, BOD, phenol, cyanide, in the waste water achieved by this treatment process were 94.9%, 96.2%, 98.3%, 94.52%, respectively and discharge effluent met the Pollution Control Board standard. On the basis of the findings schematic treatment system was finalized.

Keywords : Waste water, coke oven batteries, chemical treatment, biological treatment, COD, BOD.

Introduction

Environmental pollution is one of the most serious problems facing humanity and other life forms on our planet today. In India this problem is growing rapidly. Industrial pollution, rapid industrialization, urbanization are all worsening problems. The industrial pollution due to its nature has the potential to cause irreversible reactions in the environment and hence posing a major threat to our very existence. Untreated and improperly treated waste from different industry causes pollution. The importance of coal carbonising industries from India's national point of view is great and also growing^{1,2}.

In coke ovens, naturally found coal is converted into coke. Water is used in large quantities for quenching hot coke and washing of gas produced from the ovens. Thus, liquid effluents generated during the process operations

are highly polluted and difficult to handle. However, coke-plant waste waters contain ammonia, cyanide, thiocyanate, and many toxic organic contaminants such as phenols mono and polycyclic nitrogen containing compounds and PAHs^{3,4}. As a result this effluent shows high value of TSS, BOD, COD¹. Certain industries are unable to meet their permitted discharge limitations. Untreated discharge may alter the physical and chemical composition of environment. Due to this increment it is essential to find out an effective and economic treatment of wastewater for pollution control.

The aim and objectives of the study was (i) to focus on the characteristics of the effluent produced by coke oven plant and (ii) to find out an appropriate treatment procedure to achieve a depletion of pollutants for discharge to surface water bodies after meeting the level of standard.

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

Materials and method :

The sources of effluent for coke oven plant are Ammonia scrubbing water, Coal Tar Separator water, Quenching water, Gas Plant water. This study was done initially separating ammonia of raw effluent through natural zeolite for ammonia scrubbing water. After this treatment the treated water was mixed with coal tar separator effluent, quenching effluent and gas plant effluent for chemical treatment followed by two stages aerobic biodegradation process and finally adsorption process by activated carbon and maturation pond.

At first, pH, TSS, COD, BOD, phenol, cyanide of mixed waste water were measured. The instruments used in the experiment were Jar Test Apparatus, D.O. Meter, Spectrophotometer, COD Digester, pH meter, Pilot scale plant etc.

In this study the treatment process involved physical, chemical, biological and tertiary treatment process⁵. The chemicals used in treatments are given below.

Chemicals used :

- (1) Lime solution (10%)
- (2) Sodium hydroxide solution (5%)
- (3) Alum solution (10%)
- (4) Permanganate solution (10%)
- (5) Urea
- (6) Diammonium phosphate (DAP)
- (7) Activated carbon

Principle of treatment

(A) Pretreatment :

Separation of ammonia from ammonia scrubbing water by natural zeolite :

The scope of this study was removal of ammonia from the scrubbing aqueous solutions by raw and pretreated natural zeolite, Transcarpathian mordenite under static and dynamic conditions. The cation exchange capacity of the Transcarpathian mordenite regarding ammonium ions was evaluated as 1.64 meq/g at 1000 mg/L initial NH₄-N concentration. The dynamic exchange capacity exceeded one estimated in equilibrium study at the same initial concentration that may be conditioned by the constant removal of ion exchange products. Ammonium uptake rate was controlled by particle diffusion with diffusion coeffi-

cients determined in the range of 0.7–3.6 × 10⁻¹² m²/s. Efficiency of ammonium sorption may be improved by slowing down of initial solution rate in the column test and non-significantly by NaCl and HCl pretreatment of the mordenite.

After this pre treatment the water was mixed with coal tar separator effluent, quenching effluent and gas plant effluent for chemical treatment.

(B) Chemical treatment :

Chemical oxidization by KMnO₄ :

Chemical oxidization in waste water treatment typically involves the use of the oxidizing agent such as potassium permanganate to bring about change in the chemical composition of a compound or a group of compound. The use of this chemical oxidization was for the reduction of COD and BOD along with phenol.

Half reaction :

The oxidation of phenol is known to take place by a stepwise mechanism. However, oxalic acid may be expected as a major final product. The stoichiometry of permanganate oxidation may thus be represented as follows.

Precipitation by lime and alum :

Here lime will be added for maintaining the alkalinity required to react with alum as well as to increase the pH value. Then alum will be added to water in the presence of alkalinity, which will produce aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc, that will settle slowly through the waste water and will sweep out the suspended solid as well as reduce the level of COD and BOD and finally neutralization of waste water.

When lime alone is added as a precipitant the principles of clarification are explained by the following reactions.

A sufficient quantity of lime must therefore be added

to combine with all the free carbonic acid and with the carbonic acid of the bicarbonates (half bound carbonic acid) to produce calcium carbonate, which acts as the coagulant.

When alum is added to waste water containing calcium and magnesium bicarbonate alkalinity, the reaction that occurs may be illustrated as below.

The insoluble aluminum hydroxide is a gelatinous floc that settles slowly through the waste water, sweeping out suspended material and producing other changes.

In different experiments with different composition of various chemicals was tried for chemical treatment.

In the bench scale type 1 lit of mixed effluent water was taken and permanganate solution was added to keep for oxidation reaction. After reaction and settling the supernatant solution was collected and lime and alum solution was added to bring the pH around 7.5–8.0.

Biodegradation :

The chemically treated effluent water was taken in different types of biodegradation process.

(C) Aerobic treatment :

A bench scale batch type aerobic reactor was used for carrying out the study of treatment taking the chemically treated effluent. Specific aerobic bacterial stain was developed and used in the system. The system was provided with compressed air as per requirement round the clock. The sample was collected time to time to see the % degradation of organic load. MLSS was maintained at 2000–3000 mg/L. The aerobic treatment was done in two stage and found that 48 h of retention time in 1st stage and 4 days in 2nd stage will be more appropriate one to bring down the BOD level below 30 mg/L.

(D) Tertiary treatment :

In tertiary treatment the clear effluent from aerobic treatment was passed through a column of activated carbon. After activated carbon column the clear effluent was collected and analyzed. Two activated carbon columns in series were suitable in achieving the best result in the tertiary system.

Tertiary maturation or low rate stabilization ponds

may be constructed to provide for secondary effluent polishing and seasonal nitrification. The biological mechanisms involved are similar to other aerobic suspended growth processes. Operationally, the residual biological solids are endogenously respired and ammonia is converted to nitrate using the oxygen supplied from surface reaeration and from algae. A detention time of 18 to 20 days has been found as the minimum period required to provide for complete endogenous respiration of the residual solids.

Systems description :

The effluent water generated mainly from ammonia scrubbing section, coal tar separation system, quenching and gas plant unit. At first ammonia scrubbing water passing through natural zeolite bed for ammonia separation. Then zeolite treated water mixed with another three water generated from coal tar, quenching and gas plant section.

The mixed water will be first brought to an equalization tank. From equalization tank the effluent will be lifted to Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor No. 1 (CSTR-1) where potassium permanganate (KMnO_4) solution will be added to oxidize the organic portion of the effluent. The effluent passed to Primary Settling Tank No. 1 for proper precipitation. The overflow from Primary Settling Tank No. 1 will be brought to CSTR No. 2 where lime solution will be added to increase the alkalinity. The overflow will be brought to CSTR No. 3 where appropriate quantity of alum solution will be dosed for coagulation. The overflow from CSTR No. 3 will then be brought to Primary Settling Tank No. 2 where the precipitation of the coagulated mass will occur. The precipitation will be settled at the bottom of the Tank as sludge which will be brought to sludge drying bed by gravity.

The clear liquid from Primary Settling Tank No. 2 will be brought to Aeration Tank No. 1 where primary aerobic biodegradation of biodegradable organic part of the effluent will occur. The overflow from Aeration Tank No. 1 will be brought to Secondary Settling Tank/Clarifier No. 1 where biological mass will be settled at the bottom. A part of the sludge will be recycled (by a sludge pump) back to the Aeration Tank No. 1 for recycling and other part will be brought to sludge drying bed. The clear effluent from the Secondary Settling Tank No. 1 will be brought to Aeration Tank No. 2 where second stage aerobic biodegradation will occur. The overflow from Aeration Tank No. 2 will be brought to Secondary Settling

Tank No. 2, where biological mass will be settled at the bottom. A part of the biological sludge will be back to the Aeration Tank No. 2 to maintain the MLSS of the effluent at desired level. The other part will be brought to sludge drying bed.

The clear liquid from Secondary Settling Tank No. 2 will pass through two activated carbon beds in series and finally discharge to maturation pond. After maturation pond the treated water will be recycled or discharge. The schematic diagram is given in Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

The manufacturing processes for coke generate considerable quantities of waste water to be discharged to the sewer and irrigation channel. These effluents are characterized by high COD and BOD, cyanide, phenol⁶. Table 1 shows the water quality of the mixed waste used for the treatment. Different dosing of chemicals are showed in Table 2. Changes in the process parameters after treatment are depicted in Table 3. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps are given in Table 4.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of treatment plant for coke plant effluent.

Table 1. Characteristics of mixed effluent before treatment for coke oven plant

pH	9.78
TSS (mg/L)	214.5
COD (mg/L)	2199
BOD (mg/L)	675
Phenol (mg/L)	60
Cyanide (mg/L)	12.8

Chemical treatment

The system included waste water neutralization, pH adjustment. The goals of the system were neutralization, pH adjustment and to reduce suspended solid as well the level of COD and BOD. Physicochemical treatment can be considered as a suitable option for the treatment of coke plant effluent¹. In the present study an attempt had

Table 2. Different dosing of chemicals

Expt. No.	Dosing chemicals	Reduction in (%)				
		TSS	COD	BOD	Phenol	Cyanide
1.	5 ml KMnO ₄ solution (10%) + 1 ml lime (10%) + 5 ml alum (10%)	42.0	23.0	20.0	45.0	-
2.	10 ml KMnO ₄ solution (10%) + 2 ml lime (10%) + 8 ml alum (10%)	48.0	30.0	26.50	65.0	1.56
3.	12 ml KMnO ₄ solution (10%) + 3 ml lime (10%) + 10 ml alum (10%)	53.0	32.50	31.0	80.0	1.56
4.	15 ml KMnO ₄ solution (10%) + 4 ml lime (10%) + 12 ml alum (10%)	58.0	36.88	33.33	91.1	2.34

*Treatment : 1 L of sample + 15 ml 10% of KMnO₄ (settling time 2 h) --- Supernatant + 4 ml 10% lime + 12 ml 10% alum (settling time 30 min) ---- Supernatant for biological treatment.

Table 3. Characteristics of mixed effluent after treatability study by chemical and microbiological treatment

Water sample	pH	TSS (mg/L)	Phenol (mg/L)	Cyanide (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)
(A) After chemical treatment*	8.2	90	5.35	12.5	1388	450
(B) After 1st biological treatment						
(i) After 24 h	7.8	65	4.5	9.0	1148	338
(ii) After 36 h	7.6	58	3.2	6.5	825	195
(iii) After 48 h	7.3	45	1	3.0	540	120
(C) After 2nd biological treatment						
(i) After 72 h	7.3	38	BDL	1.0	285	68
(ii) After 96 h	7.2	35	BDL	BDL	165	40
(D) After activated carbon	7.2	25	BDL	BDL	135	35
(E) After maturation pond (expected results)	7.3	42	BDL	BDL	110	25

*Treatment : 1 L of sample + 15 ml 10% of KMnO₄ (settling time 2 h) --- Supernatant + 4 ml 10% lime + 12 ml 10% alum (settling time 30 min) ---- Supernatant for biological treatment.

Table 4. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps of treatment

Water sample	TSS (%)	Phenol (%)	Cyanide (%)	COD (%)	BOD (%)
(A) After chemical treatment*	58.0	91.1	2.4	36.88	33.33
(B) After 1st biological treatment (after 48 h)	21.0	7.2	76.5	38.56	48.8
(C) After 2nd biological treatment (after 96 h)	4.6	-	15.62	17.05	11.85
(D) After activated carbon	4.6	-	-	1.36	0.74
(E) After maturation pond (expected degradation)	(-) 7.9	-	-	1.13	1.48
	80.3	98.3	94.52	94.9	96.2

Fig. 2. Showing (%) depletion of TSS in different steps of treatment. RW = raw water; CT = chemical treatment; BT = biological treatment; AC = activated carbon, MP = maturation pond; Limit - 100 mg/L.

Fig. 3. Showing (%) depletion of phenol in different steps of treatment. RW = raw water; CT = chemical treatment; BT = biological treatment; AC = activated carbon, MP = maturation pond; Limit - 1.0 mg/L.

been made first to remove ammonia from the scrubbing aqueous solutions by raw and pretreated natural zeolite. This pretreatment was effective to remove the ammonia and similar to study by Qasim⁷ where waste water passed through a bed of clinoptilolite (a zeolite resin), which selectively removed the ammonium ion. Ghose⁸ suggested

a physicochemical mode of treatment for coke plant effluents by addition of lime slurry in a secondary sedimentation tank, while efficient ammonia removal might be achieved by synthetic zeolite columns.

The conventional process used to treat coke oven waste water includes chemical neutralization⁹. For mixed efflu-

Fig. 4. Showing (%) depletion of cyanide in different steps of treatment. RW = raw water; CT = chemical treatment; BT = biological treatment; AC = activated carbon, MP = maturation pond; Limit - 0.2 mg/L.

Fig. 5. Showing (%) depletion of COD in different steps of treatment. RW = raw water; CT = chemical treatment; BT = biological treatment; AC = activated carbon, MP = maturation pond; Limit - 250 mg/L.

ent potassium permanganate was applied as oxidizing agent such as to bring about change in the chemical composition of the liquid followed by chemical coagulant alum in the presence of alkali, as a pretreatment which produced aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc that settled slowly through the waste water and swept out the suspended solid. From Table 2, it was shown that among different

dosing 15 ml KMnO_4 solution (10%) along with 4 ml lime (10%) and 12 ml alum (10%) was best to achieve the maximum depletion. The waste water with a TSS value of 214.5 mg/L was reduced to 90 mg/L. 58.0% depletion of TSS value was observed in this step which helped in increasing the efficiency for achieving better biological treatment¹⁰. This study was also similar to the

Depletion of BOD (mg/L)

Fig. 6. Showing (%) depletion of BOD in different steps of treatment. RW = raw water; CT = chemical treatment; BT = biological treatment; AC = activated carbon, MP = maturation pond; Limit – 30 mg/L.

study of Kabdaşlı *et al.*¹¹. Throop¹² also reported that potassium permanganate was effective to reduce phenol content in waste water. The initial COD, BOD and phenol were also reduced by 36.88%, 33.33% and 91.1% respectively.

Aerobic treatment

Biological treatment may be considered as a suitable option for the treatment of coke plant effluents and control of water pollution. Prasad and Singh⁶ reviewed different treatments such as chemical and biological processes for coke oven effluent and found that aerobic biological treatment are more common in practice. To start the operation, diluted mixed waste water after chemical treatment, with COD of 1388 mg/L was introduced. Appreciable COD and BOD removal did not occur within the first 24 h of micro biological treatment. But in case of after 48 h, COD and BOD were 540 mg/L and 120 mg/L respectively. Maximum reduction of COD and BOD after 96 h was observed. Maximum depletion of 76.5% was also noticed after 48 h of biological treatment in case of cyanide whereas it showed BDL value after 96 h. Phenolic compounds and organic trace contaminants are biodegradable and hence aerobic biological treatments are most applicable treatment for coke-oven effluent⁶. In our study phenol showed BDL value after 72 h of biological

treatment. Biological removal of cyanide compound was also reported by Sirianuntapiboon *et al.*¹³.

Tertiary treatment

Sakoda *et al.*¹⁴ developed an activated carbon membrane to be used in water treatments and successfully demonstrated the decolorization of the coke furnace waste water as a model case. Activated carbon adsorption has the BOD, COD removal efficiencies¹⁵ and can be used to remove the color, odor from waste water. Zhang *et al.*¹⁶ showed enhanced carbon adsorption treatment for removing cyanide from coking plant effluent. In our present study, TSS, COD and BOD depletion of coke oven effluent obtained with activated carbon treatment were about 4.6, 1.36 and 0.74 percent respectively where as cyanide showed BDL value before introducing of activated carbon. Johnson *et al.*¹⁷ reported the ability of maturation pond. In coke oven effluent, after maturation pond, percent depletion for COD and BOD were 1.13 and 1.48 respectively.

Over all depletion of TSS, phenol, cyanide, COD and BOD after chemical, biological and tertiary treatment were 80.3, 98.3, 94.52, 94.9 and 96.2 percent respectively.

Conclusions

Coke plant effluents are one of the major contributors to the pollution. Appropriate treatment techniques includ-

ing chemical and biological treatments for coke oven effluent have been conducted due to their cost-effectiveness and environmental acceptability. From the above experiments, the best treatment process was finalized and these treatments were able to deplete the pollution load to below the permissible limit of Pollution Control Board.

So, from the study it might be concluded that chemical treatment followed by biological and tertiary treatments was the best technique for controlling pollution due to coke oven effluents. By adopting the suggested treatment scheme an effective treatment plant for coke plant effluent may be designed and the treated effluent can be recycled or safely discharged to water bodies.

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